

Large scale industrial structures conservation in China– a short report

Dr. Yiping Dong
Department of Architecture
Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University.
Suzhou, China
2015-Sep-3

Abstract

This presentation will discuss the designation, conservation practice and heritage research about the large scale industrial structures in China. Cases from Shanghai, Beijing, Huangshi, Benxi, and Tangshan, etc. will offer a general view about the big picture of industrial heritage conservation in China.

With the term of "Industrial Heritage" has been widely accepted by the Chinese conservation community, a number of industrial buildings and structures have been listed as National or Local monuments or historical buildings recently. The designation efforts by SACH have achieved great improvement in Industrial Heritage. However, the conservation practice for industrial heritage in China is very closely related to the adaptive reuse of industrial buildings/spaces in urban context, which is driven by the economic engine in creative industry or real estate development. The preservation of the large scale industrial structures encounters the challenges of lacking in concepts and professional skills.

Most of the modern industries are imported to China under a complicated historical context after the first Opium War. The industrial heritage research and discourse in China are focusing on the conservation of industrial buildings and brown field regeneration. Considerations for the environment problems of former industrial sites have faced the challenge of high cost and long remediation period. The Ruhr area cases and other western precedents have a strong influence in the regeneration proposals in China. The typical big stuff elements, steel plants and coking works', need maintenance for rust proof treatment and safety reinforcement, which are lacking adequate research and professional support yet.

Almost all the large scale industrial structures belong to state-owned enterprises. The relocation for further production, the former land redevelopment request for economic reasons, either driven by the local government or by the company, and the former workers future are composing a complicated situation for the conservation and regeneration of these structures.

The current research about industrial structures is focusing on its humanity perspectives while the values of some structures are hard to assess under the semi-colonial modern historical context in China. Taking the fact that most industrial structures in China are non-native technology, this paper argues that the localization process within the technology transfer and its transition routes research should be established for the further value assessment.

Key names:

State Administration of Cultural Heritage (SACH)	中国文物局
Beijing Coking Plant	北京焦化厂
SHOUGANG- Capital Iron and Steel Works(CISW)	首都钢铁集团
Shanghai Jiangnan Shipyard Co. Group	上海江南造船厂
Mingsheng Rd. Grain Silos	上海民生路筒仓
Huaxin Cement Plant	华新水泥厂
Qixin Cement Plant	启新水泥厂
Benxi Iron- Steel Plant	本溪铁厂
Daqing Oil Field	大庆油田